

DIGITAL TOOLS IN REMOTE TEACHING OF THE INTERPROFESSIONAL HEALTH MODULE

HERRAMIENTAS DIGITALES EN LA ENSEÑANZA A DISTANCIA DEL MÓDULO INTERPROFESIONAL EN SALUD

FERRAMENTAS DIGITAIS NO ENSINO REMOTO DO MÓDULO INTERPROFISSIONAL EM SAÚDE

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Abstract

To describe the use of digital tools in remote teaching of the Interprofessional Health Module. The Module focuses on health care from the perspective of comprehensive care and teamwork, and is offered as part of the undergraduate health courses at the University of Pernambuco (UPE) and of postgraduate tutoring. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, presential teaching activities were interrupted and resumed using remote teaching resources. Digital tools began to be used as mediators in the teaching-learning process. The main technologies utilized were: communication, support for specific disciplines, presentation, and content production. The teaching the module through remote teaching was satisfactory, with no major difficulties reported in accessing and using the technologies. Continuing activities in the remote format and the continued use of digital tools can contribute positively to academic training.

Keywords: Interprofessional education; Interprofessional relations; Information technology; Higher education; Unified health system.

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Resumen

Describir el uso de herramientas digitales en la enseñanza a distancia en el Módulo de Salud Interprofesional. El Módulo se enfoca en el cuidado de la salud desde la perspectiva del cuidado, la integralidad y el trabajo en equipo. Se ofrece a cursos de pregrado de la Universidad de Pernambuco (UPE) y tutorías de posgrado. Debido a la pandemia de Covid 19, las actividades docentes fueron interrumpidas y reanudadas utilizando recursos de enseñanza a distancia. Las herramientas digitales comenzaron a utilizarse como mediadores en el proceso. Las principales tecnologías utilizadas fueron: comunicación, apoyo a disciplinas específicas, presentación y producción de contenidos. La oferta del módulo desde la enseñanza a distancia fue satisfactoria, sin dificultades en el acceso y uso de las tecnologías. Continuar con las actividades en el formato remoto y usando herramientas digitales contribuye positivamente a la formación académica.

Palabras clave: Educación interprofesional; Relaciones interprofesionales; Informática; Educación superior; Sistema único de salud.

Resumo

Descrever o uso de ferramentas digitais no ensino remoto no Módulo Interprofissional em Saúde. O Módulo tem como foco a atenção à saúde na perspectiva do cuidado, integralidade, da atenção e trabalho em equipe. É ofertado aos cursos de graduação em saúde da Universidade de Pernambuco (UPE) e a tutoria a pós-graduação. Devido à pandemia da Covid 19, as atividades de ensino foram interrompidas e retomadas mediante uso de recursos de ensino remoto. Passou-se a utilizar ferramentas digitais como mediadoras no processo de ensino-aprendizagem. As principais tecnologias utilizadas foram: comunicação, apoio a disciplinas específicas, apresentação e produção de conteúdo. A oferta do módulo por meio do ensino remoto foi satisfatória, não sendo registradas grandes dificuldades no acesso e utilização das tecnologias. A continuidade das atividades no formato remoto e prosseguir com uso de ferramentas digitais contribuem positivamente na formação acadêmica.

Palavras-chave: Educação interprofissional; Relações interprofissionais; Tecnologia da informação; Ensino superior; Sistema único de saúde.

Introduction

The health interprofessional module focuses on “health care from the perspective of comprehensive care and teamwork”, and has been considered a mandatory curricular component since 2013 for students enrolled in health courses at the University of Pernambuco (Biological Sciences, Physical Education, Nursing, Dentistry, Medicine, and Public Health). Interprofessional education is proposed as a strategy for the development of collaborative skills, based on experimentation and interaction between students from different areas. It is an approach that seeks to support the integration of different knowledge and practices, through the sharing of common and specific skills, aiming at the construction of an integrated care plan (Lima et al., 2020).

The tutoring provided as part of the module also allows for a more effective relationship between undergraduate and *stricto sensu* postgraduate courses, currently considered an important indicator in the evaluation of postgraduate programs. This relationship is achieved through teaching internships carried out by master's and doctoral students, who work in the module as tutors, under the supervision of their advisors.

In March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 a pandemic, and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) were forced to rethink their teaching practices in order to continue academic semesters remotely, which highlighted the potential for applying active methodologies in teaching practices within the distance learning modality (Palmeira; Silva; Ribeiro, 2020).

From that point on, in addition to providing students with an understanding of the collaborative teamwork process, the interprofessional module considered working on comprehensive care from the perspective of dealing with the pandemic, in areas covered by Family Health Units (FHU) in the city of Recife-PE, with classes held in a virtual format and based on the use of technological resources. Remote teaching, therefore, made it possible to rethink Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICT) as tools capable of assisting in the teaching and learning process and promoting technological appropriation for teachers and students (Boell; Arruda, 2021).

The implementation of disciplines in the interprofessional module format, as described in this report, is fundamental for collaborative training in health, promoting the integration of knowledge and the construction of skills essential for comprehensive care in the UHS. Projects like this not only prepare students for teamwork, but also strengthen interactions between undergraduate and graduate students, fostering the construction of a more dynamic academic environment. Adapting to remote teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of practical teaching tools, making this module a relevant example of educational innovation that can be replicated in other higher education institutions. In this sense, the objective of the current article is to describe the use of digital tools in remote teaching in the Interprofessional Health Module.

Methods

This is a descriptive experience report on the use of digital tools in remote teaching in the Interprofessional Health Module at the University of Pernambuco. The organization of the report begins with an explanation of the design of the module and its organizational characteristics, followed by the presentation of the activity schedule and the evaluation process. The technologies employed are detailed under topics including: Communication Technologies, Subject-Specific Support Technologies, Presentation Technologies, and Content Production Technologies.

Development

The Module has a total workload of 76 hours and is timetables on Tuesday mornings, from 8 am to 12 pm, according to the UPE academic calendar for each academic semester. During the pandemic, the activities were carried out remotely, with synchronous and asynchronous meetings. The teaching staff is made up of tutors and preceptors, who accompany students throughout the Module. There are at least two tutors for each class tutors, who work remotely with two subgroups in the coverage area of a FHU.

Management, planning, and evaluation meetings of the pedagogical process are part of the activities between the preceptors and tutors of each class (continuing education), while students are offered class time (synchronous) and study time in subgroups (asynchronous). The contents of the program are distributed into two moments, according to the learning objectives, that are developed through the activities detailed in the schedule and lesson plans, as explained in the Table 1 below:

Table 1 - Schedule of continuing education activities.

SCHEDULE OF MODULE ACTIVITIES			
Activity	Format / Tool	TUTOR Activity	STUDENT Activity
1	Synchronous Google Meet	- Permanent Education Meeting	----
1.1 The Module, the students and coexistence	Synchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Present the proposal for the Interprofessional Module in slides, with an emphasis on its completion (developing teamwork - intervention). - Coexistence pact with students (attendance at both class times), including the importance of knowing the student handbook. - Students divided into subgroups: A, B, C, D, and E meet and choose a coordinator (manages the meeting).	- Make a coexistence pact- Understands how the Module works. - Participate in the proposed activities. - Agree on the communication format in the group and subgroups. - Listen to the instructions on the next Activity - Searches the module website (interprofissional.upe@gmail.com) for documents on the history of their future profession and the course's NCG, for individual reading and filing.

2	Asynchronous Google Meet	- Meeting: The professions chosen by the students, their practices in health promotion and the importance of teamwork - the students' view.	- Access the module website to read the course PPP focusing on the NCG graduate profile and individual registration.
2	Synchronous Google Meet	- Listen to the groups' presentations and complement them with the theory of what a field and core of knowledge is. - Provide guidance for the next activity.	- Present the work developed in the group, reflect on what they have in common and what is specific between the professions based on the stories and NCG of the chosen courses. - Receive guidance on the next activity.
3	Asynchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Meeting: Interprofessional training and the Unified Health System.	- Watch the films: "SICKO and the History of Public Health in Brazil" and discuss the questions posed by the tutor.
3	Synchronous Google Meet	- Watch the presentations of each group and debates about interprofessional and collaborative teamwork in the UHS: its value in health care practices in Primary Care. - Provide guidance for the next activity.	- Presents the group work developed on the understanding of interprofessional work and the UHS.
4	Asynchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Meeting - Seminar - The health work process in an interprofessional and collaborative team, considering the expanded concept of health in times of pandemic in the Unified Health System - UHS.	- Individual reading of the defined texts and each subgroup prepares the Seminar: The health work process in an interprofessional and collaborative team, considering the expanded concept of health, prevention and health promotion in times of pandemic at UHS.
4	Synchronous Google Meet	- Coordinate the seminar presentations and encourage debate on the topic. - Provide guidance for the next activity.	- Each subgroup presents the Seminar and participates in the debate.
5	Asynchronous Synchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Meeting: The work of health professionals in an interprofessional and collaborative team in the UHS PC in the fight against the pandemic. - Instructs to watch the video of professionals in the PC and then reinforces the concepts about collaborative interprofessional teamwork and health prevention and promotion in times of pandemic. - Provides guidance on the next activity.	- Watch the professionals' video and discuss with the tutors, aiming to understand the interprofessional and collaborative work in Primary Care at UHS.
6	Asynchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Meeting: Collaborative interprofessional teamwork in tackling the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in primary care for presentation in poster form.	- Prepare the Poster for presentation.
7	Synchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Guidance for groups in creating posters. - Provide guidance on the next activity and how the self-assessment works, providing the electronic form via a link.	- Joint preparation of the poster with the tutor, participate in the debate on the topic. - Receive instructions for the next activity and assessment.
8	Asynchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Monitors students' self-assessment and carry out their assessment in the Module.	- Carry out a Self-Assessment of their own participation in the Module via electronic form.

9	Synchronous Google Meet Classroom	- Coordinate the Final Poster Presentation. - Lead students to evaluate the Module orally.	- Final Poster Presentation. - Evaluate the Module through Conversation.
10	Asynchronous	- Student Assessment (grades and attendance)	----
11	Synchronous	- Apply Final Test	- Those who do not attain an average of 7 take the Final Test.

Caption: NCG: National Curricular Guidelines. UHS: Unified Health System. PC: Primary Care. SARS-COV2: Coronavirus (Covid19 - acute respiratory infection). **Source:** Authors (2022).

From this perspective, pedagogical activities are based on the work of Paulo Freire: Pedagogy of Autonomy (Freire, 1996), and take place from a methodological approach, focused on the critique of reality, in the search for awareness, in the development of a process where the subject becomes capable of apprehending the dialectical unity between him/herself and the object of teaching. Therefore, the problematization of social practice is the option adopted to follow this path together with the students, as a way of developing the learning objectives in an integrated manner: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor.

The activities are preceded by planning meetings that aim to actively and participatively construct knowledge among teachers (preceptor and tutor) for the training of students. Through remote teaching, with synchronous and asynchronous activities, it was possible to problematize based on the approximation with the reality of each area of knowledge, corroborating other authors, where the sum of individual skills is enhanced when working together with others, generating superior collective competence (Soares; Souza; Campos, 2016).

In the interaction and communication between the team, the domains common objectives of the formation of collective work; shared responsibility for the final success; and promotion of innovation in performance, contribute to the unity of the team (Agreli; Peduzzi; Bailey, 2017). Thus, the organization and development of interprofessional work start from the understanding of these aspects. Consequently, these factors were part of the evaluation process.

Students were assessed by the tutors throughout the semester and also performed a self-assessment, called “daily monitoring”. The grade at the end of the semester corresponded to the weighted average between the three dimensions of the learning process: Knowledge (weight two), Attitudes (weight four), and Skills (weight four) developed.

The Knowledge assessment was carried out in groups and individually, using the arithmetic mean of the performance scores in the reports and presentations of the asynchronous moments, seminar, and final project. Attitudes were recorded according to the following attributes: Interpersonal and group communication; Organization of thought and language; Ethical stance; Commitment to the construction of knowledge; and Participation. Skills were evaluated according to competencies: Understanding the interprofessional field and professional roles; Developing strategies and/or materials to contribute to interprofessional action in health promotion; and Demonstrating the ability to interact and collaborate in teamwork in healthcare. The activities were evaluated on a scale of zero to ten and the final work was the result of a collaborative interprofessional team task, being presented in poster form in the final activity of the Module.

After describing all the activities carried out, the tutoring experience confirmed that the experience of isolation and social distancing made it possible to implement innovative pedagogical practices (Barboza et al., 2021). Teachers and students were faced with the challenging reality of the emergency insertion of remote education, mainly related to the use of technologies, which, although present in educational institutions, had not yet been used as the main teaching resource (Silva Ellery; Silva Neto; Santos, 2020). Despite this, during the implementation this remote Module there were no major difficulties in accessing and using emerging technologies, either by teachers or students, which was also due to the collaborative work. However, moments of unstable internet connection were recurrent and are common in this scenario.

Digital tools were already popular socially before the pandemic and had been contributing to educational needs in light of institutional demands for technological innovations, such as teaching and learning methodologies (Carneiro et al., 2020). Thus, the transformation of the Module to a 100% remote format was a significant learning moment for teachers. Corroborating the teachers' report on the use of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), students indicated learning from the intensification of collaboration with colleagues, the adaptation of methodological strategies for remote teaching, and the use of creativity in teaching (Godoi; Kawashima; Gomes, 2020). Below, figure 1 depicts the digital tools used during the semester in the Module:

Figure 1 – Digital tools used in the Interprofessional Module.

Source: Authors (2022).

Communication technologies

The use of the Google Meet platform was possible throughout the Module, and enabled active interaction between students through previously scheduled meetings. Initially, a unique link to access the meeting was created, which was later fixed in the module description on Google Classroom for easy viewing. The tool allowed the sharing of material based on the projection of the computer screen itself; interaction via chat or microphone; and the removal of doubts via the “raise your hand” feature.

WhatsApp was used by students as a communication tool, through the creation of chat groups, which enabled the organization of activities and sharing of materials. In this regard, the application allows different media to be sent, such as: images, audios, and videos. There are other important features, such as: making calls, attaching documents, maps, among others. As WhatsApp enables communicative action between tutor-student and student-student, there is also sharing of information, the formulation of ideas, and the resolution of problems (Alencar et al., 2015; Moreira; Simões, 2017).

- Technologies supporting specific disciplines

Initially, students enrolled in the Module were added to Google Classroom via direct invitation sent by email. Upon acceptance, the student was directed to the bulletin board on the home page, as well as a tab for posting activities, to which a deadline could be assigned, with flagging of late submissions. It is likely that the popularity of Google Meet in remote teaching is mainly due to the ease of use of the tool, as is the case with Google Classroom. In addition, it is clear that free access from computers or mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, encourages teachers and students to adopt these digital platforms (Limeira; Batista; Bezerra, 2020).

The self-assessment questionnaires were created via Google Forms and consisted of a feedback strategy that, by mutual agreement, was required to be answered at the end of each synchronous class. In this way, tutors were also able to monitor student attendance, commitment, and participation, based on the number of feedback returns provided by students. Google Forms is an application that can create forms using a spreadsheet on Google Drive, with the aim of making classes more attractive and participatory. In addition, the questionnaires created are stored on the Google Server, and can be accessed from anywhere, without taking up space on the computer (Mota, 2019).

Microsoft Excel, in turn, helps the tutor to create spreadsheets and graphs, which are fundamental elements in organizing grades, recording attendance, and graphically representing statistical data. Excel is easy to use and facilitates interactive learning, through the production of interactive spreadsheets that require the insertion of formulas and, from previously inserted data, build graphs with a variety of options: column graphs, bar graphs, line graphs, sector graphs, and histograms (Silva; Moura, 2019).

- Presentation technologies

With regard to presentations, Microsoft Office PowerPoint, Canva, and Prezi were the most commonly used content production technologies for creating slides. Both the classes produced by teachers and the materials created by students to

complete activities were supported by at least one of these graphic design platforms. PowerPoint facilitates the good structuring of a presentation, allowing the insertion of videos, animations, and images in the slides, which link the content covered to the student's cognitive process, and to the development of more captivating presentations, which can favor more effective participation of students during the learning process (Pires; Araújo-Jorge; Trajano, 2012; Watengãla; Salomão; Jampa, 2021).

Canva is an easy-to-use and extremely useful tool for creating images and graphics, based on a “drag and drop” system, which allows the user to create graphic content from ready-made layouts and templates. Furthermore, the aim is to develop an authorial or shared design, allowing the user to capture, build, and share their ideas and creations visually, using illustrations from reading texts and the structure of various interfaces, one of which is the use of mind maps (Damascena et al., 2019; Ferreira; Silva, 2020).

Prezi's interface is also simple, and easy to understand and allows the user to insert diagrams and the option, within each frame, to choose the modes that will be used – text only, text and image, or image only, facilitating the organization of content and the construction of infographics. In this way, the creation of screens, color choices, and the style of letters and images (including the use of images from a personal collection) to be worked on allow for a full variety of presentations (Costa; Passerino; Tarouco, 2015; Bravo; Paixão, 2013).

- Content production technologies

The use of Mentimeter enabled students to actively participate in the construction of so-called “word clouds”, as this tool encouraged reflection and discussion about the highlighted terms. Kahoot was used to improve the absorption of subjects and content through the creation of dynamic games and tests.

The use of the Mentimeter Platform in teaching practices brings the concept of gamification to the classroom, combining competition and the dynamics of games with learning. Among its features, the best known is the “Word Cloud”, in which the teacher establishes a question and the students add keywords (expressions) that answer this question. The size of the words that are repeated by more than one student are then enlarged in the cloud (Brocardo; Domenico, 2022).

Kahoot is an application where users can register to create questions and activities, and students can also access activities created by their teachers. The most common activities on Kahoot are Quizzes and Jumble, as they allow students to score points if they answer correctly and quickly, creating a kind of classroom game (Bottentuit Junior, 2017).

Challenges and Possibilities

As a first challenge, we highlight the adaptation of students to higher education via remote learning. Given this fact, communication and guidance in activities were always reinforced, such as, for example, providing moments to clarify doubts, questions, and considerations. The dependence on a good internet connection was a limiting factor, which generated moments of instability and hindered the full participation of some students. In addition, the experience in the remote environment involves direct interaction, compromising, in part, the development of interpersonal skills, which are fundamental for interprofessional teamwork. Although digital technologies have expanded the scope of teaching and led to innovation of methodologies, it is essential to consider the need for a balance between the use of DICTs and face-to-face interaction, in order to mitigate negative effects and ensure broad training.

The digital tools used in the Interprofessional Health Module were shown to be essential during remote teaching, but it is important to critically reflect on their advantages and limitations. Google Meet and WhatsApp facilitated communication, enabling synchronous and asynchronous interactions, which are essential for the continuity of activities. Google Classroom and Google Forms allowed for efficient organization of content and assessments. Mentimeter, Kahoot, PowerPoint, and Canva were used to create an interactive and dynamic environment, facilitating active student participation. This encouraged collaborative learning and allowed for greater integration of content, bringing theory and practice closer together in a fun and dynamic way.

These technological tools have improved the teaching-learning process, providing greater flexibility and accessibility, in addition to stimulating the relationship between students and tutors, maintaining the schedule of academic activities. Another

aspect to be mentioned is the development of digital skills, both students and teachers were able to improve their technological skills through practice, adapting to new educational demands and using digital tools for presentations, organizing activities and evaluating academic progress.

The replication of this model of the **Interprofessional Health Module** in other Higher Education Institutions demonstrates the potential to advance the training of professionals who are better prepared for the challenges of the job market, encouraging a more dynamic educational practice connected to technological innovations and the demands of the Unified Health System (UHS). In addition to presenting innovation in the educational field, by integrating collaborative methodologies and the use of digital technologies in the teaching-learning process.

Conclusion

The use of digital tools as mediators in the teaching-learning process, from the perspective of the Interprofessional Module, was characterized as a key factor for the development of the academic semester in view of the need for social restrictions imposed by the pandemic. The students demonstrated ease of use and familiarity with most of the tools presented. It was found that the possibility of use of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, in addition to the computer, favored adherence to this teaching modality, as they are communication and information technologies in common use.

Adaptation to technological resources enabled the Module to be developed satisfactorily, without losing sight of the basic purpose of the syllabus, which is collaborative work in an interprofessional team. The proposed group activities, based on the socialization of undergraduate students from different areas of health, facilitated the development of interpersonal relationships and the understanding of interdisciplinary work. By exemplifying these innovative and effective practices, this module serves as a model to be replicated by other Higher Education Institutions, standing out for its ability to prepare students for teamwork in the healthcare context.

The transition from exclusively remote activities to in-person return and the adoption of a hybrid format in health education brings new challenges and opportunities. Experience with the use of digital tools during remote teaching has

proven to be fundamental for the continuity of interprofessional practices, providing greater accessibility, flexibility, and integration between the different fields of health. With the return to in-person learning, the hybrid format emerges as a promising possibility, combining the best of both worlds: direct interaction and technological facilities. Digital tools, when well integrated, can enhance collaborative learning and the development of interprofessional skills, preparing students in a more complete and effective way for the challenges of the job market. Therefore, the use of these technologies should not be seen only as a temporary solution, but rather as a strategic resource for the future of health education.

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